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What can we learn about multi-hazard impacts from global disaster records?

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Title

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Highlights

- Multi-hazards can be associated with 78 % of total economic damages, 83 % of total people affected, and 69 % of total deaths reported in the global emergency events database EM-DAT from 2000 – 2018.
- On average, a reported hazard pair has at least as much impact as a reported single hazard. Hazard types and impact types affect whether the impact of a hazard pair is even higher than the combined impact of two single hazards or not.
- We conceptualise four archetypes to describe patterns of compounding impacts from multi-hazards (“the whole is greater than the sum of its parts”, “the whole equals the sum of its parts”, “one part determines the whole”, and “the whole and the parts are limited by total impact”, see Figure).

Recommendations

- We propose further investigation and development of archetypes to describe patterns of compounding impacts from multi-hazards and guide the integration of multi-hazard interrelationships into multi-risk assessments.
- Standardised impact reporting procedures need to be established and implemented to document multi-hazards and their impacts sufficiently and consistently. This is essential for advancing the disaster risk field and for translating findings into effective policy recommendations for risk assessment and reduction.

Context

Recent studies report that multi-hazards and compound events can have disproportionately higher impacts than single hazards showing that potential, complex interaction effects between multiple risk elements cannot be neglected in risk assessment and management. Because our current understanding of multi-hazard impacts is primarily based on case studies of individual events, we perform a comprehensive analysis of historic global disaster records considering nine hazard types (floods, extreme winds, earthquakes, landslides, cold waves, heatwaves, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions and droughts). We develop an algorithm to identify multi-hazards based on the EM-DAT and GDIS databases, and assess their share in total reported direct impacts. We also statistically assess differences and similarities in direct impacts of hazard pairs, single hazards, and combinations of two single hazards.

Illustration/Graph/Picture

Figure: Overview of main research outcomes

Want to know more?

- **Link to paper:** <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-2751-2025>
- **Full reference:** Jäger, W. S., de Ruiter, M. C., Tiggeloven, T., and Ward, P. J.: What can we learn about multi-hazard impacts from global disaster records?, Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci., 25, 2751–2769, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-25-2751-2025>, 2025.
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